

A Modular Architecture for Simulating Autonomous Underwater Vehicles in OMNeT++

Carl Pommerencke, Willi Brekenfelder, Helge Parzyjegl, and Peter Danielis

Institute of Computer Science

University of Rostock

18051 Rostock, Germany

firstname.lastname@uni-rostock.de

Abstract—Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) are leveraged in a growing number of application domains such as oceanographic research, underwater archeology, environmental monitoring, and offshore infrastructure maintenance. For developing new autonomous features or cooperation strategies for multiple AUVs, simulations play a crucial role as the actual vehicle is not put at any risk. In this paper, we design a modular simulation architecture for AUVs to ease the development process and foster the reuse of existing models and components. Our architecture is derived from the structure of on-board software of actual AUVs. In a case study, we demonstrate the versatility and extensibility of the architecture by simulating and gradually expanding a conventional mission for a single vehicle to a more complex leader/follower scenario involving two AUVs.

I. INTRODUCTION

An Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) is an uncrewed vehicle designed to operate underwater without direct human control. AUVs are usually propelled by electric motors or thrusters and vary in size from smaller lightweight units up to larger complex platforms. They can be equipped with various sensors and scientific instruments (e.g., bathymetric LiDAR, cameras, sonar systems, CTD sensors) and be used in a wide variety of environments ranging from shallow coastal waters to the deep sea. Since AUVs are able to operate for extended periods without human intervention, they are well suited for long-term missions or for exploring remote and inaccessible areas (e.g., beneath large ice floes in polar regions). With increasing degrees of both versatility and autonomy, AUVs become a reliable technology for a growing number of application domains such as oceanographic research [1], underwater archeology [2], environmental monitoring [3], and offshore infrastructure maintenance [4].

Dedicated simulations play a crucial role for planning AUV missions and for improving an AUV’s autonomous behavior. Moreover, they are even essential for developing new cooperation strategies that enable multiple AUVs to efficiently solve complex tasks together for which a single AUV is not sufficient or requires considerably more time. This is because simulations allow both the behavior and the environment of the AUVs to be specifically changed, monitored, and analyzed without exposing the actual vehicle to risk. This way, developers and engineers can safely revise and fine-tune algorithms and strategies before building prototypes and conducting experiments in testbeds or carrying out field tests.

OMNeT++ [5] offers a simulation environment for event-based simulations with which the (discrete) behavior of an actor as well as its collaboration with other actors can be investigated. However, OMNeT++ lacks a basic model of a (generic) AUV in which such cooperation strategies and algorithms can be integrated and implemented. In this contribution, we thus present our efforts of porting and reusing (parts of) the DUNE runtime environment [6] for unmanned systems within OMNeT++ simulations. Besides a runtime environment, DUNE already provides basic modules for control, navigation, networking, sensing, and actuation and, thereby, shaping a generic AUV architecture for model integration.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section II provides an overview of DUNE’s modular architecture and analyzes the interactions between its components. Based on these insights, we develop our own modular simulation architecture for AUVs in OMNeT++ in Sect. III. In the case study presented in Sect. IV, we gradually expand a simulation mission for a single AUV to a more complex leader/follower scenario demonstrating the flexibility and versatility of our approach. Finally, Sect. V concludes the paper.

II. ANALYSIS OF DUNE

The Underwater System and Technology Laboratory (LSTS) at the University of Porto develops an open source software toolchain for unmanned vehicles including AUVs [7]. This toolchain includes the projects Neptus [8], Ripples [9], DUNE [6], and IMC [10]. In the following, we first provide an overview of the LSTS toolchain, then analyze DUNE in greater detail, and finally summarize our key findings.

A. LSTS Toolchain

Neptus is a graphical command and control software [8] that supports AUV operators throughout the entire mission lifecycle. This includes mission planning, monitoring, and control during mission execution as well as subsequent analysis of mission logs and results. Ripples [9] is a web framework for sharing the collected data in the cloud making it available for project stakeholders and external collaborators in realtime. DUNE [6] is a development and integration framework for the onboard software of autonomous vehicles addressing navigation, mission control, maneuvering, communication, and interactions with sensors and actuators. Finally, IMC [10]

specifies the communication protocol and the control messages exchanged not only between Neptus, Ripples, and DUNE, but also among the different modules within DUNE itself [11].

B. DUNE Architecture

DUNE is a well maintained and documented project including scientific papers and presentations explaining general ideas [7]. It provides a modular abstraction layer implemented in C++ and is designed to be compatible with various CPU architectures (e.g., x86, ARM, or MIPS) and operating systems (e.g., Linux, FreeBSD, or RTEMS). The logic for operating individual AUV subsystems (e.g., sensors, actuators, or controllers) is organized in tasks that run isolated from each other in their own thread of execution and can be scheduled periodically. Each task defines listener methods to be called at specific moments in a task's lifecycle (e.g., on creation/destruction or on activation/deactivation) or when scheduled to execute. Implementing a task thus boils down to overriding these inherited and usually empty methods with the task's specific logic.

In DUNE, tasks interact by using a publish/subscribe mechanism to exchange control messages. For this purpose, a task registers those IMC message types it wants to consume, whereas producers are free to publish any type. This loose coupling of cooperating tasks is a key concept of DUNE, facilitating its component-based design and significantly contributing to the framework's easy extensibility and high versatility.

C. Task Interactions

One downside of the publish/subscribe mechanism is its indirect addressing scheme which makes it difficult to trace the exchanged messages. It is challenging to identify which task is sending messages to which other tasks, let alone understand their interactions. With over 371 tasks and approximately 220K lines of C++ code, DUNE is too large for manual analysis. An automated analysis of the communication behavior is also difficult. The use of C++ templates complicates the determination of the IMC message types being sent or received by a task. In particular, it is necessary to consider preprocessor directives and infer types to accurately identify message types. Fortunately, the C++ compiler handles this when generating object code from source files. Therefore, we instructed the Clang compiler to output its internal Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) with type annotations in JSON format instead of generating object code. Please note that these JSON files are extremely large, ranging between 450 and 900 MB for a single DUNE task, resulting in approximately 500 GB of AST data for a full compilation run.

There are two reasons for this large size. First, although a DUNE task may have less than 100 lines of code, the preprocessor can expand it to several thousand lines by recursively resolving all include directives. Second, the JSON format's heavy indentation results in a lot of white space. Due to the latter, it is recommended to compress the files, which typically reduces them to about 1.5% of their original size.

The AST data can then be processed automatically. In each file, we search for a declaration of a DUNE task and then look for the methods `dispatch` and `bind`. The `dispatch` method publishes a message of given type, whereas the `bind` method registers a message handler for a specific type. The result is a list of message types sent and received for each DUNE task. By combining these lists, we can construct the communication graph of the DUNE framework representing the message flow between tasks. We store this communication graph for further analysis using a graph visualization and exploration tool.

Figure 1 shows visualizations of DUNE's communication graph using the graph tool Gephi [12]. In the Fig. 1(a) on the left, the entire communication graph is depicted. DUNE tasks are represented by red nodes, whereas IMC message types are shown in green. Nodes with a high degree (i.e., many incoming and outgoing edges) are typically positioned in the center and indicate important components that serve as good starting points for further exploration, for example, as shown in Fig. 1(b).

D. Analysis Results

By ranking DUNE tasks by their node degree in the communication graph, it becomes easy to identify key components that bundle a significant amount of control logic. These are usually tasks related to mission control and vehicle piloting which require extensive sensor input and generate numerous control messages for lower-level controllers or actuators. Representing these tasks as individual components in a simulation model is sensible. Conversely, many tasks have a low degree producing or consuming only a few message types. These tasks often pertain to specific sensors or actuators. To simplify simulations, it makes sense to aggregate these sensors and actuators into larger components that provide all functions for navigation and movement, respectively.

Please note that the `Control/UAV/Ardupilot` task, shown in the center of Fig. 1(b) is special. This task provides an interface to the `ArduPilot` [13] installed on the vehicle which is an open-source autopilot software suite for controlling autonomous vehicles including AUVs. In this case, DUNE dislocates the complex autopilot computations to a more specialized software. Since we do not intend to include `ArduPilot` in our `OMNeT++` simulations, we need to develop a simpler solution.

III. A MODULAR ARCHITECTURE FOR SIMULATING AUVS

A modular simulation architecture facilitates the modeling, development, testing, and integration of increasingly complex AUV systems by breaking them down into manageable and interchangeable components. After introducing the simulation environment `OMNeT++` and giving an overview about the AUV simulation architecture, we describe each of its components in greater detail.

A. `OMNeT++` Simulation Environment

`OMNeT++` [5] is an open-source, discrete-event simulation framework written in C++ that is widely used in both academia and industry. While it is generally application-agnostic, it is

Figure 1: Visualizations of DUNE’s communication graph: (a) full communication graph including all tasks (red nodes) and message types (green nodes); (b) enlarged central section of a subgraph with task and message labels.

primarily employed for simulating communication networks and networked systems, as there are well-established simulation models available for industrial communication protocols as well as the entire Internet protocol family [14]. The framework includes its own Integrated Development Environment (IDE), which is well suited for developing custom simulation models. This is supported by the framework’s Network Topology Description (NED) language that enables developers to compose new components from existing building blocks and new modules. The IDE’s graphical capabilities, featuring 2D and 3D animations, allow users to visualize and explore the state of running simulations and aid in better understanding both the simulation framework and the simulated system.

The inherent component-based design of the framework makes OMNeT++ well-suited for supporting a modular simulation architecture for AUVs. Furthermore, OMNeT++ components interact through message passing, closely mirroring the interactions of tasks and subsystems in DUNE. However, simulating continuous physical movements, such as AUV maneuvers, in a discrete event simulation is generally challenging. Interpolations and approximations may introduce a certain degree of inaccuracy. Since our primary focus is on discrete behavior patterns and cooperation strategies for AUVs and groups thereof, this is not a critical issue.

B. Architecture Overview

The primary reason for DUNE’s extensibility and versatility is its internal publish/subscribe communication infrastructure based on IMC messages exchanged between tasks and subsystems. To facilitate a similar modular simulation design, we also use an Inter-Module Communication (IMC) component that adopts DUNE’s publish/subscribe mechanism as the basis for communication. While most of an AUV’s functional logic is distributed across many fine-grained tasks in DUNE (cf.

Fig. 1a), we have consolidated related functions into larger simulation components for simplicity. This approach does not prevent developers from breaking these components down further when necessary.

Figure 2 provides an overview of our simulation architecture and its components derived from DUNE. The blue box on the right shows the subsystems of an AUV. The Inertial Navigation System (INS) collects data on location, heading, and depth from its sensors. This information is sent to the Waypoint Controller (WPC), which generates steering commands to navigate toward the current waypoint. These commands are then sent to the Propeller and Rudder Unit (PRU), which controls the AUV’s actuators. Once the WPC determines that the current waypoint has been reached, it notifies the Mission Controller (MIS). The MIS holds the mission plan, consisting of a series of waypoints, and tracks the mission’s progress. If the mission is not yet complete, the MIS selects the next waypoint for the WPC to target. Please note that although we have depicted direct communication links between these components, all information exchange actually occurs indirectly via the IMC.

Figure 2: Basic architecture of simulation model.

Outside the AUV, on the left, the Physics Engine (PE) is added to close the control loop between the PRU and the INS as shown by the dotted lines. With each Timer (TIME) tick, the PE advances the simulation and ensures that the steering commands affect the navigation sensor inputs.

C. Simulation Components

It is possible to compile the entire DUNE project into a library that can be used within OMNeT++ simulations. This allows for the convenient reuse of DUNE's utility functions, such as those for handling coordinates. However, this approach is not particularly beneficial for several reasons regarding component implementations. First, as mentioned above, simulation components contain functional logic from multiple, more fine-grained tasks in DUNE. Second, DUNE tasks are implemented as processes with a duration, whereas simulation components in OMNeT++ are event-driven and process events such as received messages instantaneously. Third, DUNE tasks include a significant amount of boilerplate code specific to DUNE, such as the handling of configuration parameters, which OMNeT++ manages differently. These are the primary reasons, we decided to implement an independent, yet similar, component concept in OMNeT++. In the following, we describe each of our architecture's components (cf. Fig. 2) in more detail.

a) Inter Module Communication (IMC): The IMC handles all of the communication between the AUV modules in OMNeT++. It works as a publish/subscribe broker and transmits messages belonging to a specific type to the correct subscribers. Publishers and subscribers are all other components as shown in Fig 2.

b) Inertial Navigation System (INS): The INS provides all information needed for the AUV to calculate the next steps. Location including the current depth are set as coordinates in a three dimensional coordinate system. The orientation consists of Euler angles around the body-fixed coordinate axes of the AUV. Orientation and location are sent as separate messages to the WPC using the publish/subscribe service of the IMC.

c) Waypoint Controller (WPC): Using the coordinates of the next waypoint and the current location and orientation, it calculates the necessary speed and heading to reach the waypoint. If the distance to the next waypoint falls below a certain threshold, the WPC marks it as reached and sends a message to the Mission Controller (MIS) to obtain the next waypoint from the predefined plan. Based on the difference between the current state and the desired state, it also computes the servo positions for the rudders and sends these to the PRU. In addition to the servo positions, the WPC calculates the thrust required to achieve the desired speed and sends this actuation to the PRU for the AUV to adjust its speed and direction. DUNE uses ArduPilot as its autopilot [13]. However, our simulation approach is simplified, and we do not need to use such sophisticated autopilot software. This simplification makes understanding and debugging significantly easier.

d) Mission Controller (MIS): When the MIS receives a request from the WPC, it checks for the next waypoint and forwards the waypoint to the WPC. The MIS stores all

waypoints for the current mission and sequentially sends each one to the WPC as soon as the previous waypoint is reached. Once the AUV reaches the final waypoint, the mission is complete and the WPC is deactivated.

e) Propeller and Rudder Unit (PRU): After receiving the servo positions and thruster actuations from the WPC, these commands need to be executed to effect changes in the environment. As the Physics Engine (PE) is responsible for these changes, the Propeller and Rudder Unit (PRU) primarily acts as a gateway to the PE. This approach ensures easy module exchange, allowing the simulation of various AUVs with different rudder and thruster configurations.

f) Physics Engine (PE): Since the internal components need to function as in an actual AUV, the physics engine must transform the output from the PRU into coordinates and Euler angles for input to the INS. Users can choose between a simpler, more robust model or a more sophisticated model for simulating the physical behavior of underwater vehicles.

The simpler model converts the PRU's output into a vector for the AUV, which is then multiplied by the elapsed time to determine the next location. The resulting coordinates and Euler angles are sent to the INS. However, this model has limitations, as it cannot simulate the realistic behavior of acceleration or turning due to the lack of mass considerations.

The more sophisticated model addresses these limitations by applying principles from [15], [16]. Using input from the PRU, the thrusters apply force to the AUV, calculating acceleration based on the vehicle's mass. Thruster forces, which can be directed in any orientation, are calculated for each axis in the body-fixed coordinate system, as well as for rotations around all three axes. If a thruster does not apply force directly toward the center of mass, the object will begin to spin. Rudders can also manipulate rotational velocity and change angular velocity. These velocities and accelerations are combined to create a realistic movement model, making it well-suited for simulating an AUV.

IV. CASE STUDY

Leveraging our modular AUV architecture, we implemented a series of increasingly complex simulations as part of a case study. The purpose is to show the extensibility and versatility of the architecture, but also to better understand its strengths and weaknesses. We start with a simulation of a conventional mission for a single AUV that we gradually expand to a more complex leader/follower scenario for two vehicles.

A. Simulating an AUV Mission

We used Neptus [17] for planning the first AUV mission. The major part of the mission consists of a rows maneuver to systematically search or survey the seafloor of a specified rectangular area. For the rows maneuver, a couple of waypoints is set so that the AUV crosses the area back and forth in straight parallel lines (i. e., rows) similar to mowing a lawn or plowing a field. The distance between adjacent lines is chosen so that the AUV's sensor range eventually covers the whole area with minimal overlap.

Figure 3: Differences between planned and simulated path of the AUV in OMNeT++.

Figure 3 shows a screenshot of the simulation’s visualization in OMNeT++. The planned course of the rows maneuver is illustrated by the black lines, whereas the simulated trajectory of the AUV is drawn in red. The AUV’s current position is depicted by the small square in the center of the screenshot as it has not completed the full mission yet. It is clearly visible that the AUV’s trajectory deviates from the planned course, particularly at the ends of the rows, since it cannot follow rectangular corners and is doing a U-turn instead. Because of this, the rows are also not perfectly parallel. However, these imperfections can probably be tolerated as long as the sensor overlap between adjacent rows is large enough so that a full detailed map of the area’s seafloor can still be created. Otherwise, a more sophisticated maneuver requiring additional waypoints at each turning point is necessary to enable a more accurate approach to the next row.

B. Adding an Energy Model

The mission time of an AUV is directly constrained by its battery capacity. In particular for longer missions, it is thus important to determine beforehand whether the battery charge is sufficient to successfully complete the mission objectives and to allow the AUV to safely return to its recovery point. Due to the modularity of our architecture, we were able to add and integrate a battery module for simulating the energy consumption without requiring further changes to existing modules. Figure 4 shows the added battery module (BAT) in orange which also subscribes for the commands sent to the actuators in order to calculate their energy consumption.

The simulated battery has a given capacity and already considers a certain basic energy consumption of the AUV when idling. For the propulsion system as one of the major energy consumers, we also implemented a generic energy model based on a characteristic curve as a proof of concept. For this purpose, the battery module also subscribes to the control messages sent to the PRU. Based on the set speed in these messages, the instantaneous energy consumption of the engine is determined by its characteristic curve and then integrated over time. This way, the simulation keeps track of the battery’s charge status and if its level drops below a configurable threshold, the simulation is stopped signaling a

Figure 4: Architecture of simulation model with all extensions for battery management and communication to other AUVs.

mission failure. Please note that more sophisticated energy models, for example based on *power state machines* (PSDs), can be implemented and added similarly as described in [18].

C. Simulating a Leader/Follower Scenario

For missions involving multiple cooperating AUVs, modular simulation models are particularly useful as each new vehicle can be consistently modeled by using the same set of modules except for those with individual functions. To demonstrate this, we implemented a leader/follower scenario with two AUVs in which the first AUV (i. e., the leader) completes a course given by a series of waypoints, whereas the second AUV (i. e., the follower) adjusts its movements based on the leader’s actions without knowing the mission plan. To ease the latter, we equipped each AUV with an *acoustic underwater modem* for communication with which the leader is periodically broadcasting its position. These position updates are received and processed by the follower. For this purpose, we also replaced the mission module of the second AUV with a role-specific *follow-me module* that internally subscribes to the leader’s position updates from the modem module and simply sets the received coordinates as new waypoint. The waypoint module is then adjusting the follower’s course accordingly.

Figure 4 gives an overview about the module architecture used by the second AUV in its follower role. The navigation module (INS), the engine module (PRU) and the waypoint controller (WPC) are reused from the AUV’s basic architecture without any modifications (cf. Sect. III), whereas an acoustic underwater modem is added for communication (COM) and the mission module is replaced by a specific follow-me unit (FMU). Please further note that using the modem also requires the addition and management of a corresponding communication channel (CHAN) outside of the AUV as part of the simulation’s global data structures in OMNeT++.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have analyzed the architecture of the DUNE development framework and runtime environment for the on-board software of AUVs. We dissected the framework into its subsystems and modules, examined the communication graph between the cooperating tasks and, thereby, identified its

major components. Based on this analysis, we derived a modular architecture for AUV simulation models in OMNeT++. We adopted the flexible publish/subscribe communication mechanism for simulation components, but often aggregated lightweight tasks to more meaningful subsystems. In a case study, we simulated and gradually extended a conventional AUV mission by adding an energy model as well as a second AUV as part of a leader/follower scenario. Our modular architecture significantly simplified and accelerated the development process by enabling the easy reuse of components and providing clear interfaces for adding new components or replacing existing ones. In future, we want to leverage this architecture to better integrate and refine advanced cooperation strategies for multi-AUV systems into our simulations.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Y. Konoplin, A. I. Borovik, D. N. Mikhailov, Y. V. Vaulin, A. F. Scherbatyuk, A. A. Boreiko, R. A. Babaev, D. A. Bolovin, and D. I. Tregubenko, "Application of autonomous underwater vehicles for research of ecosystems in the southern ocean," in *Antarctic Peninsula Region of the Southern Ocean: Oceanography and Ecology*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2021, ch. 28, pp. 421–432, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-78927-5_28.
- [2] M. Costa, J. Pinto, M. Ribeiro, K. Lima, A. Monteiro, P. Kowalczyk, and J. Sousa, "Underwater archaeology with light auvs," in *Proceedings of OCEANS 2019 Marseille*. Marseille, France: IEEE, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1109/OCEANSE.2019.8867503.
- [3] D. O. Jones, A. R. Gates, V. A. Huvenne, A. B. Phillips, and B. J. Bett, "Autonomous marine environmental monitoring: Application in decommissioned oil fields," *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 668, pp. 835–853, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.02.310.
- [4] O. Khalid, G. Hao, C. Desmond, H. Macdonald, F. D. McAuliffe, G. Dooly, and W. Hu, "Applications of robotics in floating offshore wind farm operations and maintenance: Literature review and trends," *Wind Energy*, vol. 25, no. 11, pp. 1880–1899, 2022, doi: 10.1002/we.2773.
- [5] A. Varga, "A practical introduction to the OMNeT++ simulation framework," in *Recent Advances in Network Simulation: The OMNeT++ Environment and its Ecosystem*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2019, ch. 1, pp. 3–51, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-12842-5_1.
- [6] LSTS. (2022, Jun.) DUNE source code repository. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/LSTS/dune>
- [7] J. Pinto, P. S. Dias, R. Martins, J. Fortuna, E. Marques, and J. Sousa, "The LSTS toolchain for networked vehicle systems," in *Proceedings of 2013 MTS/IEEE OCEANS Bergen*. Bergen, Norway: IEEE, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.1109/OCEANS-Bergen.2013.6608148.
- [8] LSTS. (2022, Jun.) Neptus source code repository. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/LSTS/neptus>
- [9] A. Sá, R. Santos, R. Mendes, P. Dias, J. Pereira, W. D. Choi, A. Sérgio Ferreira, and J. B. de Sousa, "Ripples: A tool for oceanic campaign managing, supervision, and situational awareness," in *Proceedings of OCEANS 2023 Limerick*. IEEE, 2023, doi: 10.1109/OCEANSLimerick52467.2023.10244653.
- [10] LSTS. (2022, Jun.) IMC source code repository. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/LSTS/imc>
- [11] R. Martins, P. S. Dias, E. R. B. Marques, J. Pinto, J. B. Sousa, and F. L. Pereira, "IMC: A communication protocol for networked vehicles and sensors," in *Proceedings of OCEANS 2009 Europe*. Bremen, Germany: IEEE, May 2009, doi: 10.1109/OCEANSE.2009.5278245.
- [12] M. Bastian, P. S. Heymann, and M. Jacomy, "Gephi: An open source software for exploring and manipulating networks," *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 361–362, Mar. 2009, doi: 10.1609/icwsm.v3i1.13937.
- [13] Z. Luo, X. Xiang, and Q. Zhang, "Autopilot System of Remotely Operated Vehicle Based on Ardupilot," in *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Intelligent Robotics and Applications*. Shenyang, China: Springer, Aug. 2019, pp. 206–217, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-27535-8_19.
- [14] L. Mészáros, A. Varga, and M. Kirsche, "INET framework," in *Recent Advances in Network Simulation: The OMNeT++ Environment and its Ecosystem*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2019, ch. 2, pp. 55–106, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-12842-5_2.
- [15] A. Knauf, *Mathematische Physik: Klassische Mechanik*. Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 2017, doi: 10.1007/978-3-662-55776-1.
- [16] F. Landis Markley and J. L. Crassidis, *Fundamentals of Spacecraft Attitude Determination and Control*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2014, doi: 10.1007/978-1-4939-0802-8.
- [17] Neptus Developer Team. (2022, Jun.) Neptus Documentation. [Online]. Available: <https://lsts.fe.up.pt/neptus/info.html>
- [18] P. Danielis, H. Parzyjeglja, M. A. M. Ali, and F. Sill Torres, "Simulation model for energy consumption and acoustic underwater communication of autonomous underwater vehicles," *WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs*, vol. 21, pp. 89–107, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s13437-021-00253-z.